

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.2.3: Mining (minerals, metal, fossils fuels)

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Description

Section 3.3.2.3 Mining (minerals, metal, fossils fuels) assesses the role of resource extraction as a driver of biological invasions for chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5

Additional papers added to the selection (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations) n=8

Papers selected for review n=28

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: "mining" AND "invasive species" AND "driver"

Search 2: "Resource extraction" OR "mining" AND ("invasive" OR "exotic")

Search 3: "mine abandonment" AND "invasive species"

Search 4: Mine rehabilitation OR restoration and invasive species

Search 5: "Resource extraction" OR "mining" ("invasive" OR "exotic") AND "marine"

- **Search engine:**

Search 1 and 3: Web of knowledge

Search 2, 4, 5: Google scholar

- **Date:** August 2019 to November 2019

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result: 20

Search 1: 5 selected

Search 2: 4 selected

Search 3: 3 selected

Search 4: 6 selected

Search 5: 2 selected

Selection criteria:

Based on the 5 searches, 20 papers are selected by the search terms, timespan, and relevance as a driver. All papers are screened by their title and abstract and chose 20 papers to review. Remaining 8 papers are used for background information. Additional references were found by searching for specific items based on under represented taxa or regions through targeted searches.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 8

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 28 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]

-Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx